

Supplementary information

Sorption of PFAS and PFAS Precursors on Activated Carbon in Realistic Drinking Water Conditions: Insights into Sorbent Variability and PFAS Structural Effects

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1. Particle porosity measurements

The granular activated carbon (GAC) skeletal (material) and particle (apparent) densities were measured with the pycnometer with water as pycnometer liquid, as described in detail in (Sontheimer et al., 1988). With this method only the pores that are accessible to water are considered in density measurements. Around 3 g of dry GAC was weighted and placed in water which was then boiled to ensure complete wetting of GAC. The wet GAC was removed from boiling water and rolled on cellulose tissues to remove the excess water i.e., water that is present on the external surface of the particles. In this way, GAC particles whose pores are filled with water are obtained, and their mass was measured in a pre-weighted pycnometer. After that, the pycnometer was filled with water and weighted again. With the obtained masses, and known pycnometer volume, the material and particle density were calculated according to equations reported in Sontheimer et al. In the end, particle porosity was calculated from the following equation:

$$\varepsilon_p = 1 - \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_m} \quad (S7)$$

where ε_p (dimensionless) is particle porosity, ρ_p (g/L) is particle density and ρ_m (g/L) is material density

2. pH drift method

The pH drift method was used to determine the pH point (pH_{PZC}) at which the surface of carbon contains equal amounts of positively and negatively charged functional groups, i.e., surface is globally neutral. With this method, activated carbons were equilibrated with NaCl solutions of different starting pH. Because of the protonation and deprotonation of activated carbon functional groups, the pH of the solution will change, and, in equilibrium it will be constant. Experiments were performed in glass bottles containing 0.5 L of 0.01 M NaCl. The starting pH was adjusted with the addition of HCl or NaOH to be between 2-11. After adjustment, around 1.0 g of GAC was added, and the system was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 48 h. After 48 h system was in equilibrium, and longer experiments showed no significant change in the final pH. During each step of the experiment, NaCl solution was sparged with N_2 to remove the impact of CO_2 on the solution pH. The pH_{PZC} was obtained by plotting initial vs final pH, and the resulting graph is shown in Figure S.2. The point where initial vs final pH

curve crosses $y = x$ line is pH_{PZC} . For the pH below pH_{PZC} surface is positively charged, and negatively charged beyond.

Figure S1. Relationship between the PFAS carbon chain length and the time-averaged sorption for the studied PFAS to studied GAC. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the time-average sorption data and the shaded area represent the 95% confidence limits.

Figure S2. Relationship between the PFAS precursors (per-/poly-fluoroalkyl ether acids (PFEA), fluorinated sulfonamides) carbon chain length and the time-average sorption for the studied PFAS to studied GAC. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the time-average sorption data.

Figure S3. Percentage sorbed over exposure time (h) for the studied sorbents SRD, F400, and R-F400. PFAS are organized in classes: a) perfluoro-carboxylic acids (PFCA) and perfluoro-sulfonic acid (PFSA); b) fluorinated sulfonamides, per-/poly-fluoroalkyl ether acids (PFEA); c) studied branched (Br) and linear (L) isomer of both PFAS and PFAS precursors. The error bars represent the standard deviation of triplicate samples.

Table S1. The limit of quantification (LOQ) of all the targeted PFAS, PFAS classes.

<i>PFAS class</i>	<i>Compound</i>	<i>Acronym and chain length</i>	<i>Mass-labelled</i>	<i>LOQ (pg/L)</i>	
<i>perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCA)</i>	Perfluorobutyric acid	PFBA (C4)	M4PFBA	50	
	Perfluoropentanoic acid	PFPeA (C5)	M5PFPeA	50	
	Perfluorohexanoic acid	PFHxA (C6)	M5PFHxA	50	
	Perfluoroheptanoic acid	PFHpA (C7)	M4PFHpA	50	
	Perfluorooctanoic acid	PFOA (C8)	M8PFOA	-	
	Perfluorononanoic acid	PFNA (C9)	M9PFNA	50	
	Perfluorodecanoic acid	PFDA (C10)	M6PFDA	50	
	Perfluoroundecanoic acid	PFUdA (C11)	M7PFUdA	50	
	Perfluorododecanoic acid	PFDoA (C12)	MPFDoA	50	
<i>perfluorosulfonic acids (PFSA)</i>	Potassium perfluoro-1-butanedisulfonate	PFBS (C4)	M3PFBS	44	
	Sodium perfluoro-1-pentanesulfonate	PFPeS (C5)	M3PFBS	47	
	Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate	L-PFHxS (C6)	M3PFHxS	37	
		Br-PFHxS (C6)	M3PFHxS	9	
	Sodium perfluoro-1-heptanesulfonate	PFHpS (C7)	M3PFHxS	48	
	Potassium perfluoro-octanesulfonate	PFOS (C8)	M8PFOS	-	
	Sodium perfluoro-1-nonanesulfonate	PFNS (C9)	M8PFOS	48	
	Sodium perfluoro-1-decanedisulfonate	PFDS (C10)	M8PFOS	48	
<i>Precursors</i>	<i>Sulfonamide</i>	Perfluorobutylsulfonamide	FBSA (C4)	M3PFBS	50
		Perfluorohexanesulfonamide	FHxSA (C6)	M3PFHxS	50
		Perfluorooctanesulfonamide	FOSA (C8)	M8PFOS	50
	<i>sulfonamide acetic acids</i>	N-methylperfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid	L-MeFOSAA (C8)	d5-N-EtFOSAA	38
			Br-MeFOSAA (C8)	d5-N-EtFOSAA	24
		N-ethylperfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid	L-EtFOSAA (C8)	d5-N-EtFOSAA	39
			Br-EtFOSAA (C8)	d5-N-EtFOSAA	12
	<i>per-/poly-fluoroalkyl ether acids (PFEA)</i>	Sodium dodecafluoro-3H-4,8-dioxanonanoate	ADONA (C7)	M8PFOA	47
		Potassium 9-chlorohexadecafluoro-3-oxanonane-1-sulfonate	9Cl-PF3ONS (C8)	M8PFOA	47
		Potassium 11-chloroeicosafluoro-3-oxaundecane-1-sulfonate	11Cl-PF3OUDS (C10)	M8PFOA	47
		Perfluoro-4-oxapentanoic acid	PF4OPeA (C4)	M4PFBA	50
		Perfluoro-5-oxahexanoic acid	PF5OHxA (C5)	M3PFHxS	50
		Perfluoro-3,6-dioxahexanoic acid	3-6-OPFHxA (C5)	M8PFOA	50
		Potassium perfluoro(2-ethoxyethane)sulfonate	PFEESA (C4)	M3PFHxS	45

Table S2. Properties of the three types of GAC

	Density (Kg/L)	Micropore volume (cm ³ /g)	Mesopore volume (cm ³ /g)	Particle porosity (%)	pH point of zero charge
F400	0.51	0.32	0.12	50	9.4
F400-R	0.42	0.26	0.26	54	8.8
SRD	0.46	0.36	0.23	58	8.4

Table S3. Recoveries of the extraction and injection standard.

	Compound	Acronym	Recovery (SD)
Extraction standard	Perfluoro-n-[¹³ C4]butanoic acid	M4PFBA	102% (14.7)
	Perfluoro-n-[¹³ C5]pentanoic acid	M5PFPeA	86% (12.4)
	Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4,6- ¹³ C5]hexanoic acid	M5PFHxA	78% (21.2)
	Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4- ¹³ C4]heptanoic acid	M4PFHpA	81% (19.2)
	Perfluoro-n-[¹³ C8]octanoic acid	M8PFOA	83% (16.9)
	Perfluoro-n-[¹³ C9]nonanoic acid	M9PFNA	90% (21.0)
	Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4,5,6- ¹³ C6]decanoic acid	M6PFDA	81% (24.7)
	Perfluoro-n-[1,2,3,4,5,6,7- ¹³ C7]undecanoic acid	M7PFUdA	102% (33.3)
	Perfluoro-n-[1,2- ¹³ C]dodecanoic acid	MPFDoA	162% (22.1)
	Sodium perfluoro-1-[2,3,4- ¹³ C3]butanesulfonate	M3PFBS	65% (22.7)
	Sodium perfluoro-1-[1,2,3- ¹³ C3]hexanesulfonate	M3PFHxS	81% (29.7)
Sodium perfluoro-1-[¹³ C8]octanesulfonate	M8PFOS	80% (25.9)	
Injection standard	Perfluoro-n-[2,3,4- ¹³ C3]butanoic acid	M3PFBA	
	Perfluoro-n-(1,2- ¹³ C2)octanoic acid	M2PFOA	
	Sodium perfluoro-1-[1,2,3,4- ¹³ C4]octanesulfonate	M4PFOS	

Table S4. Percentage sorbed of individual PFAS on the three studied GAC for individual exposure times(1, 5, 24, 96, 240 h) and the time-averaged sorption of 1h to 240h (Av). Data represents triplicate samples, with standard deviation indicated in parentheses.

PFAS classes	Compounds	F400						R-F400					
		1	5	24	96	240	Av	1	5	24	96	240	Av
perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCA)	PFBA (C4)	14,5% (8)	17,2% (2)	22% (2)	57,1% (3)	39,2% (11)	30% (16)	28,4% (11)	28,6% (12)	17,8% (3)	32% (11)	20,3% (5)	25,42% (5)
	PFPeA (C5)	21,9% (2)	20,9% (1)	22% (1)	25,4% (1)	23% (2)	22,64% (2)	17,7% (1)	20,3% (3)	21,3% (3)	21,9% (1)	22% (3)	20,64% (2)
	PFHxA (C6)	25,3% (7)	22% (1)	18,6% (3)	25,9% (1)	17,9% (4)	21,94% (3)	12,8% (3)	21,2% (2)	20,1% (2)	19% (1)	23,5% (2)	19,32% (4)
	PFHpA (C7)	12,1% (1)	11,4% (2)	6,8% (3)	17,2% (1)	16,2% (6)	12,74% (4)	0,6% (7)	12,5% (2)	12,5% (2)	12% (2)	15,9% (2)	10,7% (5)
	PFNA (C9)	21,9% (5)	24,2% (1)	23,4% (3)	36,9% (2)	39,3% (11)	29,14% (7)	13,4% (5)	23,9% (4)	21% (4)	27% (6)	26,2% (0)	22,3% (5)
	PFDA (C10)	35,2% (3)	34,6% (4)	33,1% (4)	39,8% (2)	47,6% (12)	38,06% (5)	20,6% (9)	32,6% (3)	31,5% (5)	32,8% (7)	24,2% (12)	28,34% (5)
	PFUdA (C11)	50% (7)	49,3% (7)	46,2% (9)	45,6% (4)	60,5% (3)	50,32% (5)	28,2% (9)	42,4% (2)	47,6% (5)	37,6% (8)	29,8% (4)	37,12% (7)
	PFDoA (C12)	52,3% (8)	43,7% (7)	42,2% (11)	45% (5)	59,2% (4)	48,48% (6)	28,9% (2)	55,3% (2)	46,7% (6)	38,2% (9)	25,2% (4)	38,86% (11)
	PFPeS (C5)	18,1% (2)	12,4% (3)	18,5% (0)	26,5% (2)	23,2% (5)	19,74% (5)	9,8% (0)	11,9% (1)	4,8% (7)	16,1% (2)	21,1% (14)	12,74% (6)
	perfluorosulfonic acids (PFSA)	L-PFHxS (C6)	15,9% (2)	14,1% (1)	12,7% (1)	26,7% (2)	28,3% (5)	19,54% (7)	8% (5)	15,8% (2)	14,8% (3)	19% (2)	24,7% (14)
Br-PFHxS		19,8% (7)	12,5% (2)	17% (0)	26,3% (0)	21,7% (8)	19,46% (5)	7,7% (9)	12,7% (3)	1,6% (2)	36,2% (3)	18,4% (6)	15,32% (12)
PFHpS (C7)		21,4% (4)	10,9% (2)	11,5% (11)	21,3% (3)	32% (9)	19,42% (8)	4,4% (10)	14% (6)	24,1% (2)	21% (10)	15,3% (1)	15,76% (7)
PFNS (C9)		47,7% (9)	45,5% (7)	34,5% (12)	39,2% (3)	43,7% (14)	42,12% (5)	23,8% (11)	36,3% (2)	42,5% (6)	36,9% (1)	35,1% (6)	34,92% (6)
PFDS (C10)		54,9% (8)	57,5% (8)	43% (9)	47,9% (5)	52,7% (2)	51,2% (5)	60,9% (9)	51,6% (5)	61,2% (2)	45,5% (3)	45,6% (15)	52,96% (7)
FBSA		70% (6)	74,6% (4)	86% (8)	98,6% (0)	96,5% (0)	85,14% (11)	96,1% (1)	91% (1)	87% (3)	95,7% (0)	89,2% (4)	91,8% (4)
FHxSA		38,7% (7)	69% (15)	52,9% (12)	94% (0)	86,7% (2)	68,26% (21)	66,2% (23)	54,3% (8)	48,9% (8)	75,4% (1)	63% (5)	61,56% (9)
FOSA		11,8% (5)	17,5% (0)	23,4% (2)	82,7% (1)	25,4% (20)	32,16% (26)	18,2% (17)	33% (0)	28,8% (7)	40% (0)	24,4% (6)	28,88% (7)
L-MeFOSAA		32,1% (6)	31,4% (10)	34,8% (0)	39,7% (3)	19,1% (12)	31,42% (7)	23,1% (8)	39,1% (5)	27,2% (7)	33% (9)	32,4% (7)	30,96% (5)
Precursors per-/poly-fluoroalkyl ether acids (PF(E)A)		Br-MeFOSAA	63,2% (16)	51,2% (6)	58,2% (4)	66,4% (1)	75,6% (1)	62,92% (8)	53,7% (4)	63% (6)	69,3% (3)	66,3% (7)	53,2% (5)
	L-EtFOSAA	41,8% (8)	39,2% (11)	40,5% (9)	37,2% (5)	22,2% (4)	36,18% (7)	30,2% (11)	37,9% (2)	40% (6)	33,7% (7)	8,2% (8)	30% (11)
	Br-EtFOSAA	58,1% (18)	47,4% (6)	50,6% (4)	58% (1)	57,2% (8)	54,26% (4)	49,5% (4)	58,1% (2)	59,5% (4)	55,8% (8)	47,4% (24)	54,06% (5)
	ADONA	18,6% (6)	11,8% (5)	17,2% (3)	31,5% (2)	33,1% (5)	22,44% (8)	14,1% (12)	17,9% (16)	0,3% (1)	21,6% (2)	18,4% (25)	14,46% (7)
	9Cl-PF3ONS	25% (17)	15,4% (7)	7% (12)	0,7% (10)	30,4% (5)	15,7% (11)	4,9% (5)	9,1% (16)	18,6% (6)	13,2% (3)	10,8% (49)	11,32% (5)
	11Cl-PF3OUDS	13,9% (2)	8% (7)	19,1% (12)	3,2% (0)	14,4% (5)	11,72% (6)	2% (7)	24,5% (22)	27,6% (3)	17,9% (5)	6,2% (0)	15,64% (10)
	PF4OPeA	54,9% (2)	54,4% (0)	56,5% (3)	60,3% (0)	57,2% (1)	56,66% (2)	56,2% (2)	55% (1)	53,7% (11)	13% (1)	53,7% (3)	46,32% (17)
	PF5OHxA	57% (0)	57,8% (4)	67,2% (6)	75,7% (3)	62,7% (6)	64,08% (7)	68,7% (1)	60,1% (4)	44,3% (5)	50,1% (1)	56,9% (6)	56,02% (8)
	3-6-OPFHpA	70,1% (7)	71,2% (3)	72,7% (3)	80,6% (2)	82% (1)	75,32% (5)	74,5% (3)	69% (6)	65,2% (3)	69,8% (1)	73,9% (8)	70,48% (3)
	PFEESA	24,6% (3)	24,6% (2)	23,3% (5)	35,2% (1)	26,1% (2)	26,76% (4)	20,4% (8)	16,9% (4)	5,3% (1)	14,9% (2)	27,9% (9)	17,08% (7)

PFAS classes	Compounds	SRD						
		1	5	24	96	240	Av	
perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCA)	PFBA (C4)	18,8% (7)	18,2% (1)	10,8% (1)	29,5% (20)	16,1% (6)	18,68% (6)	
	PFPeA (C5)	19,7% (0)	19,3% (2)	21,6% (0)	24,8% (2)	25,5% (1)	22,18% (3)	
	PFHxA (C6)	19,1% (0)	16,1% (3)	20,7% (0)	20,4% (3)	25,5% (2)	20,36% (3)	
	PFHpA (C7)	10,5% (1)	6,3% (4)	9,5% (1)	13,2% (4)	19,8% (2)	11,86% (5)	
	PFNA (C9)	19,2% (2)	18,6% (8)	16,7% (2)	27,7% (8)	30,5% (10)	22,54% (5)	
	PFDA (C10)	36,5% (2)	27,3% (7)	20,8% (2)	41,5% (7)	44,1% (8)	34,04% (9)	
	PFUdA (C11)	35,5% (4)	34,6% (6)	25,9% (4)	55,7% (6)	54,1% (8)	41,16% (12)	
	PFDoA (C12)	33,1% (8)	31,4% (7)	22,9% (8)	62,5% (7)	56,4% (20)	41,26% (15)	
	perfluorosulfonic acids (PFSA)	PFPeS (C5)	21,1% (6)	9,3% (6)	1,7% (6)	16,7% (6)	24,1% (0)	14,58% (8)
		L-PFHxS (C6)	10,5% (0)	12,7% (5)	4,4% (0)	19% (5)	33,9% (6)	16,1% (10)
Br-PFHxS		9,9% (2)	25,9% (6)	3,8% (2)	15,5% (6)	28,1% (3)	16,64% (9)	
PFHpS (C7)		13,7% (3)	18,3% (7)	14,9% (3)	16,6% (7)	29% (7)	18,5% (5)	
PFNS (C9)		27,2% (9)	29,8% (6)	12,2% (9)	60,3% (6)	54,1% (12)	36,72% (18)	
PFDS (C10)		30,4% (5)	37,8% (4)	15,9% (5)	70% (4)	76,5% (5)	46,12% (23)	
Sulfonamides	FBSA	72,8% (4)	95,9% (1)	78,5% (4)	85,8% (1)	86,5% (1)	83,9% (8)	
	FHxSA	23,4% (10)	69,4% (3)	18,6% (10)	60,3% (3)	60,7% (1)	46,48% (21)	
	FOSA	23,8% (0)	15% (16)	8,5% (0)	52,5% (16)	25,1% (7)	24,98% (15)	
sulfonamide acetic acids	L-MeFOSAA	30,7% (6)	28,2% (7)	11,4% (6)	44,4% (7)	21,2% (14)	27,18% (11)	
	Br-MeFOSAA	64,6% (1)	62,7% (4)	44,4% (1)	57,8% (4)	67,7% (4)	59,44% (8)	
	L-EtFOSAA	38,6% (5)	27,3% (4)	20% (5)	53,6% (4)	49,3% (15)	37,76% (13)	
	Br-EtFOSAA	30,2% (1)	53,4% (4)	51,1% (1)	57,6% (4)	55,3% (5)	49,52% (10)	
	per-/poly-fluoroalkyl ether acids (PFEA)	ADONA	1,2% (5)	16,2% (3)	4,6% (5)	18,2% (3)	18,4% (10)	11,72% (7)
9Cl-PF3ONS		7,7% (2)	6% (5)	6% (2)	23,6% (5)	33% (14)	15,26% (11)	
11Cl-PF3OUDS		2,3% (20)	2,5% (1)	2,1% (20)	42,6% (1)	2,2% (27)	10,34% (16)	
PF4OPeA		55,9% (0)	43,7% (29)	65,7% (0)	28,4% (29)	68,6% (1)	52,46% (15)	
PF5OHxA		58,1% (1)	52,7% (4)	43,9% (1)	49,9% (4)	57,3% (3)	52,38% (5)	
3-6-OPFHpA		69,1% (1)	64,5% (1)	65,4% (1)	78,6% (1)	74,6% (2)	70,44% (5)	
PFEESA		24,8% (5)	8,8% (5)	10,4% (5)	16,3% (5)	27,4% (4)	17,54% (7)	

Reference:

Sontheimer, H., Crittenden, J.C., Summers, R.S., 1988. Activated carbon for water treatment.